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From Sailing Peace to Selling Peace: A Semiotic Study of The Product Called ‘Peace’

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Abstract:

The idea of peace has always been differently interpreted and highlighted in the various cultures of the world. At this moment while some parts of the world are engaged in wars and other violent outbursts, the propagation or promotion of the idea of peace seems essential. But at the same time, just a passive promotion of the idea sounds hypocritical as well. The capitalist side of this concrete jungle has been selling the idea of peace for their profits. Thus, this paper attempts to delve deep into the understanding of how the idea of peace is being sold as a part of world culture and how this is creating a particular virtual image of peace (that is the product). The aim of this paper is to analyse the role of the motivational speakers of India, who have been selling peace as a product to be consumed by millions of their followers by applying the exact marketing strategies that the brands use to push their sales.

Keywords: Peace, marketing, product, motivational speakers, strategies.

The notion of peace has been dealt with in literature, art and culture in ways that emphasise the attitude of the creators towards the essential presence of peace in the world. Keeping aside policy-making endeavours around the establishment of peace in the world, it is important to notice how culture at large has been instrumental in spreading the idea of peace through effective story telling. While much attention is given to the different discourses regarding their contributions in spreading words of peace, it cannot be denied that in the 21st century, social media has played an indispensable role in leaving an impact on the thoughts and actions of human beings. Everyone knows that the big business organisations and institutions use social media to mould public opinion. But when it comes to the idea of 'peace', it becomes interesting to understand how this content is sold to the public and who profits from spreading such content. Generally, when we think about the message of peace, it is always felt that the message of peace is spread in the interest of the world and not in the interest of the person who is spreading the word. In fact, it is assumed that someone who is spreading the word of peace is doing it as a kind of social service without expecting any financial gain from it. However, when we notice the same thing is being spread through social media, we cannot ignore the revenue model that is associated with the action. In this paper, I will try to analyse the role of motivational speakers in spreading the word of peace, examine their role in creating a specific image of peace, and investigate the nature of the message that is being popularised by them.

Social media has become an essential part of the 21st century culture and its tremendous power to influence public opinion cannot be ignored. It acts as an essential tool for garnering public support in any kind of social or political matter. Peace has always been one of the most crucial topics to be dealt with by poets, writers, and artists, according to their particular point of view. Moreover, every time they have worked with this topic; they have created a symbol of peace in the mind of their audiences. Among the first images that come to our minds when we talk about peace are those of a white dove, lilies, mistletoe, white poppies, olive branch and

so on. This is because history has seeded these images in our culture. As participants of that culture, we have been using these as a part of our language with the result that these images get coded in the popular consciousness. Nevertheless, with the advent of social media, a new and drastic heteroglossic perspective of peace started gaining importance in the world. If we notice the trajectory of the propagation of the idea of peace through culture, we will notice that in recent times, emphasis is put more on the microscopic manifestations of peace rather than a macroscopic understanding and appreciation of the term. There was a universality to the idea of peace which was used to be communicated earlier, but if we notice the current trends, we will find the individual is more on in focus than the collective. The topic of world peace or that of collective human peace has always been represented through literature and art however it is social media that has been effective in highlighting the significance of individual peace. Since discussions about peace of mind on a micro-level hold the potential of promoting world peace in the long run, in this journey of propagating ideas about peace of mind, the role of motivational speakers on social media is crucial.

But any discussion about social media content will remain incomplete without a consideration of the element of financial profit. No one can deny that the creators of this type of content look forward to the creation of a successful revenue model out of the uploaded materials. In this connection it is essential to consider how the issue of peace is branded as a product to be sold in the market through the social media platforms. This is because with the idea of the selling of a product, the notion of the virtual creation of an image of the product in the mind of the consumers cannot be separated. Indeed, this is the reason why it is necessary to analyse how a particular virtual image of peace is being created by social media and to what extent that image is compatible with the real significance of the idea of peace. An idea which is generally expected to be popularised selflessly, has become a product which is marketed widely through the motivational speakers. It is my intention to see how the virtual sites create

a product out of the idea of peace and how it is sold to the consumers through the interesting game of persuasion. It is likely that business centric vision force us to see peace like any other product that is to be promoted, sold and used for moulding the opinions of an audience. But an in-depth analysis of this action leads us to the understanding that such promotional tactics often destroys the real purpose of communicating the notion of peace. They produce a stereotypical image of peace, pointing only at specific aspects of peace, distracting people from the real idea of peace, and becoming like any other content which entertains audience. The ways by which social media and its engagement with the idea of peace produce specific effects, can be understood through a semiotic study of those contents.

In keeping with the traditional understanding of the 4Ps of marketing, this paper will try to show how motivational speakers in India create a product out of the notion of peace. The first P of marketing is Product and it prompts us to realise how sometimes a product is created keeping in mind what the consumers need. Also, sometimes it is created and then forced into the market and a need for the same is created (Kingsnorth 27). In the case of the idea of peace, it can be said that both these things apply. On the one hand the need for the promotion of the idea of peace seems to be needed, keeping in mind the violence and internal conflicts existing in the nation, and on the other hand it can also be assumed that peace is made into a product to be forced to the consumers keeping in mind a specific purpose. The second P being Price for understanding “price elasticity and competitive positioning,” it can be said that through the creation of content about peace, a revenue model is created through which the speakers benefit directly (Kingsnorth 28). With the popularisation of such content, the social media platforms offer monetary support to the speakers. This opens their path to get invited as guests at different events and thus get monetary benefits. Now, coming to the third ‘P’ which signifies Place, these kinds of contents are pushed to the audience through strategised internet algorithms to the specific audiences (Kingsnorth 29). Audience profiling constitutes a big part of this marketing

process because it is by depending on the search histories, identities, age groups and interests of the viewers, that the social media contents are pushed to the audience. These forced contents might create a lasting impact on the minds of the consumers. Hence, search engine optimisation is indeed a big part of the process of selling the idea of ‘peace.’ Coming to the last ‘P’ of marketing which is Promotion, it can be claimed without any doubt that each social media platform becomes an outlet through which these contents are promoted so that they reach the maximum number of audiences. It cannot be overlooked that “smart marketing is much more than shouting about your product and much more about taking customers on a journey” and that these kinds of smart marketing strategies are often adopted by the promoters of peace (Kingsnorth 31). Reflecting upon these fundamental aspects of marketing, it can be stated that ‘peace’ has indeed become a product that is rampantly sold by the motivational speakers through the different social media platforms. Other than the 4 P’s, in case of social media marketing, the role of storytelling is vital in the selling of a product (Anderson 13). Focusing on this idea, it can be realised that the motivational speakers use a lot of anecdotes and their approach to the audience is almost always teamed with different stories. They share personal stories, their own experiences, traditional stories, mythological stories and often well-known philosophical anecdotes to complement their discourses. In this way, storytelling plays an important function in the social media marketing of the contents on ‘peace.’

Of course, the question that comes up is whether ‘peace’ has become a product of social media or not. The production of contents on the idea of peace adds up to the creation of a virtual image of peace which becomes a sign for a newly constituted notion of peace. This new image, I propose, is far away from the traditional image of peace and its real purpose. This leads to the production of a biased virtual image as well. A semiotic study of the contents related to peace which are promoted by the motivational speakers will allow us to understand how the process of signification leads to the overall production of a myth of peace in recent times. For the

purpose of this research, the top five motivational speakers in contemporary India (according to number of their followers on social media) have been considered. Beginning with Sadhguru with 11 million followers, followed by Gaur Gopal Das with 7.7 million followers, Sri Sri Ravi Shankar with 4.4 million followers, Swami Mukundananda with 2.89 million followers and B.K Shivani with 1.5 million followers, the present research will show how their contents can be read as signifiers for the idea of peace, and how in the long run first order signification leads to the development of signs of peace which in the second order signification becomes new signs to produce an evolved idea of peace. Such semiotic study will allow one to decode the purpose behind such contents and reveal the meaning that is produced through the entire process.

Looking at the top five motivational speakers who have been talking about peace in different ways in their speeches, the apparent signifiers that can be located may be noted in their dress codes, appearances, different ways of speaking, gender identity and so on amidst other explicit signifiers. If we consider these signifiers for the first order signification, we will be able to notice how these signifiers are signifying the idea of peace which is being popularised in the social media. They are creating an image of peace based on these signifiers so that people will start relating these signifiers with peace. The colour saffron and white seem to be highlighted in these contents as we see these speakers mostly wearing these colours to evoke the idea of peace. Even religion is made a prominent signifier as almost all these speakers stand for one particular religion. Other than that, the way in which they speak and their gender positions also become very significant signifiers of the notion of peace.

The problem of this signification process is that in the long run the semiology of these social media contents will create a prominent myth about peace. This myth will be an exclusive one rather than a signifier of the original idea of inclusivity. If we notice the religious attachments of these top five speakers, we will be able to decode how the idea of peace is

associated with a specific religion and how this contradicts with the inclusivity of the notion. Moreover, noticing the gender of the speakers, it is clear how the process of gendering peace is also associated with and drawn upon as a part of the process. Traditionally women were always seen as the primary agents who sustain peace. But women have always been seen as the passive propagators of peace while men have been seen as active agents of promoting peace. While analysing these speakers, the same idea seems to come across prominently. While most of the male speakers walk from one end of the podium to the other or use excessive hand gestures as a part of their communication processes, the female speakers are way too composed and they seldom display such high energy. This can imply that listening to male speakers might make audience expect both spiritual lesson and entertainment while in case of female speakers it is just a journey of learning new spiritual ideas. B.K Shivani is the only female speaker whose content is popular and a prominent image of peace that she portrays is that of passivity, serenity, and tolerance in contrast to the energetic, witty, flamboyant, and spontaneous essence of Gaur Gopal Das or even Sadhguru. While discussing about the process of signification, Roland Barthes has talked about the second-order signification in “which is a sign (namely the associative total of a concept and an image) in the first system, becomes a mere signifier in the second” (Barthes 113). So, it can be said that these signs of peace when they become signifiers in the process of second order signification, the earlier signifiers function in denying the existence and validity of other diverse signifiers of peace. The signs which were produced in the first order signification are the stereotyped notions of peace which result in erasing the inclusive idea of real peace.

Keeping in mind the purpose driven motive of social media in pushing the reach of these contents, it is important to decode how the creation of new shades of peace as the signified benefits the power structures of the society by creating docile bodies that is the “body that is manipulated, shaped, trained, which obeys, responds, becomes skilful and increases its forces”

(Foucault 149). As Foucault had discussed the idea of docile bodies in relation to power structures and their propagation of discipline, the same can be applied in this matter to see how the selling of the idea of peace actually helps the dominant power structures to create passive individuals who are easier to manipulate and control. One thing to notice about the motivational speakers is that they primarily focus on discussions about inner peace, individual peace, or peace of mind. Their gaze on microcosmic manifestations of peace results in the creation of docile bodies who may discipline their urges of protest because it might affect their inner peace. They become bodies which tolerate, discipline and survive rather than protest and assert their existence. When Gaur Gopal Das states “peace means to be in the middle of all mayhem and chaos and yet to stay calm and yet to stay focussed” we realise that while focusing on private peace he is deliberately hiding the importance of getting concerned about out peace (Das 2:53). This inevitably helps the supreme power structure of the nation to govern efficiently and to manipulate people into thinking about peace in biased terms. In this way, they stimulate “the productive process wherein our surveilled bodies are encultured to this subjugation” (Loadenthal 2). The focus of individuals is diverted from the role of society, the governing organisations, and the policies in sustaining peace to the importance of maintaining individual peace of mind. It is as if world peace will be manifested only by the individual practice of peace and not depending upon the policies and decisions which are made to destroy peace.

Works Cited:

Anderson, Daniel. *Storytelling: Manipulation of the Audience*. Charlie Creative Lab Ltd Publisher. 2020.

Barthes, Roland. *Mythologies*. The Noonday Press.1972.

Foucault, Michel. *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*. Vintage Book.1995.

“How to Live at Peace With Yourself and Others.” YouTube, uploaded by Peace of Mind TV,
5 October 2018, .

Kingsnorth, Simon. Digital Marketing strategy: An integrated Approach to Online Marketing
.Kogan Page, 2016.

Loadenthal, Michael. “Social Media, Biopolitical Surveillance, and Disciplinary Social
Control: Aggregating Data to Examine Docile Bodies.” Lacanian and Foucaultian
Approaches to the Body edited by Becky McLaughlin and Eric Daffron. Jefferson,NC
:McFarland and Company, 2020.

“Peace is an ingredient in life.” YouTube, uploaded by Gurudev’s World, 28 February 2021,

“Watch This if You Want real Peace I Gaur Gopal das.” YouTube, uploaded by Gaur Gopal das,
18 June 2018,

“Your Peace in Your Control.” YouTube, uploaded by Shemaroo spiritual Life, 19 April 2018.